

Abstract

Possible cures for planetary cancer are presented, discussed, and hypothesized as likely requirement for successful neurogenesis.

Extinction as a cure

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1 Intro

So far, I have established that major mass extinctions are relative - not all complex life gets extinct, some is rather transferred to another place, in the process of neurogenesis.

However, in case of cancerous surface life, it probably has to be cured (transformed) prior to migration.

Figure 1: Rapid transit to Sheol¹

2 Depolarization

Previously, I have assumed that cancerous personalities are eliminated, either prior to, or with, transformation through accelerated evolution.

However, probability that transformation will cure cancerous nature depends on polarization of fusing lifeforms. In case cancerous nature is not healed, depolarization will likely be achieved through extinction.

Here, human society effectively divides into non-cancerous (neutral) and cancerous (polarized) population. Without neutrality, cancerous individuals would then annihilate and go extinct.

Note that no extinction is absolute, so, even here, souls are preserved but they incarnate into wild (neutral) bodies. Co-evolution of a polarized soul with a neutral body will result in a less polarized hybrid, thus subduing cancerous tendencies. If these are further energetically constrained, they will be benign.

With cycles of reincarnation these souls would then be integrating into growing neutral human society as neutral individuals.

On the other hand, if population does not separate, due to polarized individuals being a majority, this will certainly lead to destruction of all life and death of the planet - unless nature (immune system of the planet) does have some other cure to cancer and will react to specifically target cancerous individuals (eg. through viral mechanics and/or introduction of intra-terrestrial lifeforms that prey on humans).

Most likely, such mechanisms do exist in a planet (COVID-19 is then likely a precursor to more specialized viruses), it is only a question in what measure they will be exercised and how precise will the targeting be - after all, difference between a good and bad (cancerous) human is, like in case of TGF- β proteins in humans, more mental than physical.

In case of viral mechanics, DNA could have a role in this [natural] selection, while, in case of predators, fear is likely a strong factor. In any case, synchronicity should have a strong role.

A malignant tumour in human bodies usually goes undetected until the number of cells in it has doubled at least 30 times from a single cell[2]. Human population on Earth has already doubled 32 times, reaching 4.3 billion in 1978. According to current growth projections, 33rd doubling should be reached ≈ 2029 . Reactions to cancer on Earth at this point should thus not be surprising and I would not be surprised if 33rd doubling would also be the peak of human population.

Human population has reached 2^{30} sometime between 1830 - 1840. This is the time when Chinese Empire was forced to open its frontiers to western exploitation and when Industrial Revolution could be fully felt[3]. The Industrial Revolution has been criticised for complete ecological collapse, causing mental illness, pollution and unnatural systems of organizing for humanity. Industrial Revolution has turned humanity and nature into slaves and it is destroying[4] the world[5]. It has also been criticised for valuing profits and corporate growth over life and well-being, multiple movements have arose philosophically against the Industrial Revolution and include groups such as the Amish and Primitivism[6]. So, it seems the cancer indeed becomes noticed at 2^{30} population size, correlated with its industrial revolution.

Therefore, separation is probably a less painful solution.

Figure 2: Relative prophecy

Fig. 2 could be showing rebuilding of [neutral] population that would stay on the current planet, rather than migrating to another as I have hypothesized elsewhere.

However, both could be true (superposition).

3 Horizontal transfer and transformation (extermination)

Similar to correlation of major extinctions with vertical transfer and transformation of life, death can be correlated with horizontal transformation and transfer of souls.

Current extermination of wild life on Earth's surface is thus only relative extermination, as souls of these creatures cannot be destroyed, proportionally to the decrease in wildlife population these souls will be increasingly coupling with bodies of humans and other domesticated animals.

Probability for expression of *wild* personality will thus grow in domesticated species (incl. humans).

This may be interpreted as a self-correcting mechanism, raising intelligence/awareness (*wild* souls are generally non-polarized) in destructive species to prevent further destruction of wild habitats and generally wild (free) species.

However, major extermination is generally a precursor to major extinction, thus, rise in awareness among cancerous species will likely require extinction in order to be reflected in rise of consciousness.

4 Programmed disease

It is well known that embryogenesis is very similar to carcinogenesis. If Earth is in the embryonic stage of development (as I hypothesize), the development of cancer on surface may be programmed. Any complex organism is formed with the *fossilization* of symbiosis of multiple organisms into genetic code of a new organism.

In this process of evolution even a disease could be used to advance the development of a being. The fact is, we are all born with viruses and diseases (some are part of DNA), they are just normally not a problem, they're either not expressed or they're subdued by the immune system, at least until old age or until the system is weakened.

Now consider that Earth needs significantly increased CO₂ for its development at times (as ancient history suggests). Rather than using volcanoes from the start, perhaps it would be better to let disease develop and produce it. This is a perfect solution if development of this disease can be halted before it becomes too dangerous. It's even better if this disease is suicidal and halts itself.

The evidence suggests evolution of life (including human evolution) is locally programmed (even though one cannot see the physical code). There are examples of inverted causality where life seems to have been adapted to increase in CO₂ even before it happened.

This strongly suggests that increased CO₂ is simply part of the programming. Increases of atmospheric CO₂ are correlated with major extinctions (which should also be programmed) and a major extinction is happening now too.

Therefore, I find it unlikely that human domination on surface and anthropogenic CO₂ emissions are an unplanned excursion, rather, it is a normal part of genetic expression in planets like Earth.

If that is so, and humans do not produce as much CO₂ (or greenhouse gases) as needed, one can expect increases in volcanism and other natural greenhouse gas emissions - even as anthropogenic CO₂ emissions decrease.

Indeed, evidence suggests this might already be happening[7].

This does not mean *we* should continue drilling for oil and increase pumping of greenhouse gases - it would be better to leave that to Earth if more of it is indeed needed, otherwise it could become fatal for everyone (if it is not fatal now). After all, *we* do not know how much is needed and *we* obviously have trouble controlling ourselves.

Disease going out of control should not be desirable - even if *we* are the disease.

References

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